

CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS FOR IMAGE RECOGNITION

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Abstract. The purpose of the work, the results of which are presented within the framework of the article, was to study modern architectures of convolutional neural networks for image recognition. The article considers such architectures as AlexNet, ZFnet, VGGNet, GoogleNet, ResNet. A characteristic of the quality of image recognition for a neural network is the top-5 error. Based on the results obtained, it was revealed that at the moment the network with the most accurate result is the ResNet convolutional network with an accuracy rate of 3.57%. The advantage of this study is that this article gives a brief description of the convolutional neural network, and also gives an idea of the modern architectures of convolutional networks, their structure and quality indicators.

Keywords: convolution, filter, structure, subsample, activation function.

Introduction. The widespread development and spread of computer vision technologies entails changes in other professional areas of human life. Convolutional neural networks are used in object and face recognition systems, special medical software for image analysis, navigation of cars equipped with autonomous systems, security systems, and other areas. With the growth of the computing power of personal computers, as well as the advent of image databases, it became possible to train deep neural networks (deep neural networks). In the problem of image recognition, convolutional neural networks (Convolutional Neural Networks) are used. The purpose of the article is to review

modern architectures of convolutional neural networks for the problem of image classification. One of the tasks of machine learning is the problem of image classification. To classify an object in an image means to indicate the number to which the recognized object belongs. To evaluate machine learning algorithms, labeled image databases are usually used, for example, CIFAR-10, ImageNet, PASCAL VOC. Due to the fact that several objects can be present on images, for example, in the ImageNet image database, and only one is marked (annotated), the main error criterion is a top-5 error. Those. it is considered that the algorithm was not mistaken if the correct category of the object is among the five categories given by the algorithm as the most probable. Hence, many neural networks for image classification are estimated using the top-5 error [1]. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are used for optical pattern recognition, image classification, object detection, semantic segmentation, and other tasks. The foundations of the modern SNS architecture were laid in one of the first networks - LeNet-5 by Jan LeKun. The structure of a convolutional neural network The convolution network is a multilayer perceptron (perceptron, English perceptron from Latin perceptio - perception [2]) is a mathematical or computer model of information perception by the brain, created to recognize 2D surfaces with a high degree of resistance to scaling, transformations, and other types of deformation. Learning to solve such a problem is carried out with reinforcement, while networks of the form are used, the architecture of which corresponds to the following restrictions [2]. Feature extraction. Each neuron receives input from a local receptive field in the previous layer, extracting its local features. Once a feature is retrieved, its location does not matter, as approximately established its location relative to other signs. Feature display. Each computational layer of the network consists of a set of feature maps. Each feature map is shaped like a plane on which all neurons must share the same set of synaptic weights. This form of structural constraint has advantages. Displacement invariance. Bias invariance is implemented by feature maps using small kernel convolution which performs the function of "flattening".

Subsample. Each convolution layer is followed by a computational layer that performs local averaging and subsampling. By means of local averaging, resolution reduction for feature maps is achieved. Such an operation leads to a decrease in the sensitivity of the output signal of the feature mapping operator, as well as to bias and other forms of transformations. Figure 1 shows a diagram of a convolutional network consisting of one input, four hidden and one output layer of neurons. This network was created for image processing, in particular for handwriting recognition. The input layer, consisting of a matrix of 28×28 sensor nodes, receives images of various characters that are pre-centered and normalized in size. After that, the computational layers alternately implement the convolution and subsampling operations. The first hidden layer performs the convolution. It consists of four feature maps, each of which is a matrix of 24×24 neurons. Each neuron corresponds to a field with a sensitivity of 5×5 . The second hidden layer performs the local averaging operation as well as subsampling. It also consists of 4 feature maps containing 12×12 matrices. Each neuron has a 2×2 receptive field, a sigmoidal activation function, an adjustable threshold, an adjustable coefficient. Adjustable coefficient and threshold determine the working area of the neuron. For example, with a small coefficient, the neuron operates in a quasi-linear mode. The third hidden layer performs a repeated convolution operation. The layer consists of 12 feature maps, each of which is a matrix of 8×8 neurons. Each neuron of the third hidden layer can have synaptic connections with different feature maps from the previous hidden layer. The fourth hidden layer performs a second subsampling and local averaging operation again. The layer consists of 12 feature maps, however each feature map contains a matrix of 4×4 neurons. The output layer performs the final convolution step. The layer consists of 26 neurons, each of which corresponds to one of the 26 letters of the Latin alphabet. Each neuron corresponds to a 4×4 receptive field [4]. Convolutional Neural Network Architectures for Image Classification AlexNet is a convolutional neural network that won the ImageNet LSVRC2012 competition with a margin of error of 15.3%.

The network had a partially similar architecture to the LeNet network from J. Lekun, but was deeper, with a large number of convolutional layers. The network consisted of 11x11, 5x5, 3x3 convolutions, maximum pooling, dropout, data augmentation, ReLU activation function, SGD (Stochastic Gradient Descent) with momentum. The application of the activation function occurred after each convolutional and fully connected layers.

Figure 1 - AlexNet architecture

Shown in Fig. 1. AlexNet architecture, includes 8 layers with weight coefficients, where the first 5 layers are convolutional, the next 3 are fully connected. The output of the last fully connected layer is fed to the softmax activation function, which performs the distribution over the class labels. Next, the network maximizes the multinomial logistic regression target, which is the same as maximizing the training average of the log-likelihood of the correct label in the prediction distribution. Using stochastic gradient descent with a learning rate of 0.01, a momentum of 0.9, and a weight reduction of 0.0005. The learning rate is divided by 10 times the accuracy plateau, also decreasing by a factor of 3 during the learning process.

Formulas to Update Weight Factors

The update of the weights (w), where i is the iteration index, v is the momentum variable, and ϵ is the learning rate, is shown in the diagram. The learning rate was chosen equal for all layers, and also corrected manually during

the entire training. Next step was to divide the learning rate by 10 when the number of validation errors stopped decreasing. AlexNet shows the result of top-5 errors - 15.3%, respectively. ZFNet is the winner of ILSVRC 2013 with a top-5 error of 11.2%. The main role in this is played by hyperparameter tuning, namely the size and number of filters, packet size, learning rate, etc. M. Zieler and R. Fergus proposed a system for visualizing kernels, weights, and latent representation of images. The system was named DeconvNet. The network architecture of ZFNet is almost identical to the architecture of the AlexNet network. The essential differences between them in architecture are as follows: – ZFNet filter size and stride in the first convolutional layer in AlexNet is 11×11 , stride is 4; in ZFNet - 7×7 , step is 2; is the number of filters in pure convolutional layers of the network (3, 4, 5).

Figure 2 - ZFNet architecture

VGGNet In 2014, K. Simonyan and E. Zisserman from the University of Oxford proposed a neural network architecture called VGG (Visual Geometry Group). VGG16 is an improved version of AlexNet, in which large filters (sizes 11 and 5 in the 1st and 2nd convolutional layers) are replaced by several 3x3 filters one after the other.

Figure 3. VGGNet network architecture

During training, the input to ConvNets (Convolutional networks - convolutional neural networks) is an RGB image of a fixed size of 224×224 px.

In the next step, the image is passed through a stack of 3x3 convolutional layers. One of the VGGNet network configurations uses 1x1 filters, which can be thought of as a linear transformation of the input channels. The convolution step is fixed at 1 pixel. The padding of the input of the convolutional layer is chosen such that the spatial resolution is preserved after convolution, i.e. the padding is 1 for 3x3 convolutional layers.

Spatial pooling is done using five max-pooling layers that follow one of the convolutional layers (not all convolutional layers have subsequent maxpooling). The max-pooling operation is performed on a 2x2 pixel window with a step of 2 [13]. After the stack of convolutional layers, there are 3 fully connected layers: the first two layers have 4096 channels each, the third layer has 1000 channels (because in the ILSVRC competition it is necessary to distribute objects into 1000 categories). The last layer is softmax. All hidden layers are equipped with a ReLU activation function. The authors have demonstrated that building blocks can achieve certain results in the ImageNet competition. The number of top-5 errors decreased to 7.3% [6].

Figure 4. - Architecture of GoogleNet

A convolutional network from Google (GoogLeNet) known as Inception-v1 is the winner of ILSVRC 2014 with a top-5 error of 6.7% [Szegedy et al., 2015]. All convolutions in the network, including those inside Inception modules, use straight-line linear activation. The network has 22 layers when only layers with parameters are counted. The total number of layers used to build the network is 100. Switching from fully connected layers to a medium pool improved the top-1 accuracy by about 0.6%, however the use of dropout remained necessary even after the fully connected layers were removed. Given the depth of the network, the

ability to propagate gradients back across all layers was an efficient task. The high performance of smaller networks in this task suggests that the features produced by the layers in the middle of the network must be very discriminatory. When adding auxiliary classifiers associated with these intermediate levels, discrimination at lower levels in the classifier was expected. This helped overcome the vanishing gradient problem by providing regularization. The classifiers in the network take the form of small convolutional networks placed on top of the output of the Inception modules. During training, their loss is added to the total network loss with weight. During inference, these auxiliary networks are discarded. More recent control experiments have shown that the influence of auxiliary networks is relatively small (about 0.5%) and that only one of them is required to achieve the same effect. The exact structure of the complementary network, including the auxiliary classifier, is as follows: – a middle pooling layer with a filter size of 5×5 and a stride of 3, resulting in an output of $4 \times 4 \times 512$ for (4a) and $4 \times 4 \times 528$ for (4d) cascade; – 1×1 swivel with 128 filters for size reduction and direct linear activation; – fully connected layer with 1024 units and direct linear activation; – discarded layer with 70% discarded output ratio; – line layer with softmax loss as a classifier (predicts the same 1000 classes as the main classifier, but removed during inference).

Conclusion

The spread and development of computer vision technologies entails a change in other professional areas of human life. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are used in object and face recognition systems, special medical software for image analysis, navigation of cars equipped with autonomous systems, in security systems, and other areas. With the growth of computing power of computers, the advent of image databases, it became possible to train deep neural networks. One of the main tasks of machine learning is the problem of image classification. CNNs are used for optical recognition of images and objects, object detection, semantic segmentation, etc. In this article, the most common

architectures of convolutional neural networks for the problem of image recognition, their structure and features were considered. As a result of the analysis of the architectures, it was revealed that the ResNet-152 convolutional neural network showed the best result in the image recognition task, with a top-5 indicator of 3.57%, which indicates a fairly accurate object definition. A feature of the ResNet architecture is that the convolutional layers have 3x3 filters, and that a fast connection has been added to the network, which turns the network into its residual version.

References

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